

Optimising and storing energy in Europe's homes and buildings

- ★ Designing better systems for energy use in buildings will be essential for Europe to meet its target of near zero energy in 2050. Technical Project Coordinator, **Pavol Bodis** of SCORES explains how new combined technologies can collect renewable energy locally, store it and use it in smarter, more optimised ways to improve efficiency.

The building sector accounts for 40% of the total European energy consumption. It's the big challenge and barrier when forming strategies for the ambitious sustainability goals set by the European Union. The SCORES project sees a solution in renewable energy generated locally and self-consumed by buildings.

A hybrid storage system of electricity and heat could be the answer, bridging gaps in supply and consumption and all at cost effective rates. The project looks at using renewable energy produced by local solar panels and wind farms combined with advanced heat and electricity storage systems and supported by an Energy Management System. This approach allows stored energy to be used when the renewables can no longer provide it because the sun is not shining, or the wind is not blowing. There are a range of solutions and combinations of different technologies on the table and all could play a key role, depending on the needs of the local market in any given country.

"We want to switch to renewable energy, specifically for urban environments where there are houses and buildings. On a global scale, you want to have as much energy generated locally, such as solar panels on the rooftops. But sometimes the sun does not shine and our plan is to store the energy when you have an abundance of it and use it when the sun doesn't shine. This is the whole idea. It can be done with our hybrid energy system," explains Pavol Bodis.

By local, one could mean an individual building or a district consisting of several buildings. The properties are still connected to the Grid and the energy can also sent back to the Grid in some circumstances. The difference is, there is more local, cyclic and

The SCORES concept is based on a hybrid system combining solutions that harvest electricity and heat from the sun, store electricity, convert electricity into heat, store heat, and manage the energy flows in the building.

renewable energy being put to use and in a way that it is not wasteful, rather it is stored and used when and where needed.

There are key technologies that entwine together to make this kind of production, storage and optimisation of energy consumption possible.

SCORES is actively pursuing **involvement in policy for several countries** to understand **how their solutions can apply** in government set **frameworks**, to their **goals** and **within budget requirements**.

Smarter technologies for energy optimisation

An integral component that adds intelligence into energy usage is the Building Energy Management System (BEMS) which relies on clever algorithms to predict all kinds of things, from when the sun is shining, how much energy is used by a building's inhabitants and how to best optimise supply to meet demand. There are many kinds of smart systems available on

the market but SCORES has one that has a buffering system which helps households store the energy when they have an excess of it, making it available when there may be a lack of it being collected. Another component part of such a hybrid system is a heat pump. Somewhat more advanced solar-driven technology,

namely solar thermal technology in the form of PVT tiles on a rooftop can support the functioning of a heat pump in a property.

"The heat pump is a device that converts electricity to heat and provides efficient heating that is driven by green electricity in our case. For optimisation, self-produced electricity comes via these specialised PVT cells put on individual buildings," said Bodis. "Effectively, this produces electricity and

heat which goes into the heat pump, which in turn converts it into the heat that is used for heating up water. The real big chunks of energy at home are hot water and heating of the house, potentially about 80%."

Heat pumps are being looked at seriously as technologies of promise for widespread adoption by some European governments.

There are many innovations that can make up a hybrid storage system. One innovation championed by SCORES is the REDOX heat battery, essentially a battery that stores heat rather than electricity.

"There are technologies where we have basically taken a technology from one industry, for example, the chemical process industry, and we transferred it into the energy storage system, the REDOX heat technologies are an example of that. It is currently in a laboratory testing phase and we are testing the performance for

housing, so it's not technology that is ready for implementation in the commercial world yet.

"We have also adopted a storage technology based on phase change materials. This is material that changes its state from liquid to solid and if you do that you need to put energy in it and when it goes back you release the energy from it. So that means by changing the phase or form of the material you can store energy, we do that as well."

Another key focus of the project, one crucial for emissions targets and green goals in a worldwide perspective, is materials recycling, specifically with batteries. All batteries run down and eventually become inefficient and unusable. Prolonging battery life or finding alternative uses for older batteries needs to be a priority with such a growing industry, so as not to create a new problem around disposal.

Promoting circular use of materials

"We have second hand reused electrical batteries from buses," said Bodis. "For mobility application for a bus, these batteries are no longer optimal, they don't last long or work so well for bus transport, but we can refurbish them and reuse them and give them a second life. We give them a second home in someone's actual home."

"For our society it's not just that energy has to be renewable but also the materials we use should be circular, which means to close the circle of materials and not just unearthing new raw materials. We extend the lifetime of the batteries by years. With our application it is not so important to have the highest energy density. For our purposes the battery can be at 60-70% but on a vehicle that is a real problem as you don't want to have a huge wait to charge it with only 60% capacity, but in a stationary

Demonstration of the integrated hybrid energy system takes place in two real buildings representative of different climate and energy system configurations. One in Northern Europe (Austria) and one in Middle/Southern Europe (France).

SCORES

Self Consumption Of Renewable Energy by hybrid Storage systems

Project Objectives

The main goal of SCORES is to demonstrate in the field the integration, optimization and operation of a building energy system including new compact hybrid storage technologies, that optimizes supply, storage and demand of electricity and heat in residential buildings and that increases self-consumption of local renewable energy in residential buildings at the lowest cost.

Project Funding

The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 766464.

Project Partners

You can find information about the project and its partners with the following link:
• <http://www.scores-project.eu/about>.

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Erwin Giling is the coordinator of the SCORES project, working in close cooperation with technical coordinator Pavol Bodis. For well over a decade Giling is developing and managing projects in the field of CO₂ reduction, energy storage, energy conversion and the electrification of the industry.

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application it works fine. When we started this, battery life was limited, but we have seen huge developments in lithium-ion batteries in the meantime, so it is a good idea to use these second-hand lithium-ion batteries that have a far longer lifetime now, compared to when we started SCORES. We will also account for that in the business case analysis, as the world changes. When we started SCORES, PV panels were very expensive and now, four years later, they are only 20% of that original price. Costs are going in a positive direction for economic viability."

SCORES is looking at several smart ways to use combinations for optimal benefit from the perspective of self-consumption. An important aspect of SCORES, is that there is more than one way to create a hybrid energy storage system, this is not focusing on one single configuration. The project is looking into several types to work out how to combine technologies and how they can work together in efficient ways. There is also a cost element for each technology which in the real world, is a very important factor for uptake and use.

Making systems feasible

"Developing these systems for the European market does not mean that you have the same solution for every country, for every climate situation or for the same scale for that matter. We can't test for every variation and country but we do have two implementations. The choice we made was a relatively large-scale implementation in the South of France and we've applied our system in two large buildings consisting of 150 apartments, set up for the climate in the Mediterranean. The other one is close to the mountains in Austria, so it is completely different, with a more continental type of climate, where we have a smaller scale system for six houses."

Beyond testing how the system works, there is the broader question around its practicality and feasibility. The question of,

can this be rolled-out across Europe and the world? Developers, contractors, governments and existing homeowners would need to be invested and willing. Re-fitting existing housing stock alone could run into big numbers, potentially multiple millions of buildings that have to be refitted, many which are old buildings. This presents an extreme challenge, one which Bodis recognises.

"What we do see from the projects around us is the renovation rate lags behind the needs for the transformation of the building stock. Also, in Germany there are not enough companies to rebuild as quickly as excel sheets tell us. So, what to do? Our approach in this respect is testing in various configurations and modelling how to make the biggest steps with the smallest amounts of resources."

SCORES is actively pursuing involvement in policy for several countries to understand how their solutions can apply in government set frameworks, to their goals and within budget requirements.

"In the SCORES project you have complex systems with so many types of devices, so many functionalities for your home, but you should also see this as the platform for the message, where in certain situations you can apply this or that part of the system. It doesn't mean you can make optimal solutions for every house in every country but, what we are proving that you can find an optimal, minimalistic approach with limited resources."

The research findings will be extremely useful for what comes next in the coming decades, where if Europe does not find workable solutions to the challenges SCORES seeks to tackle, the goals around emissions reductions will surely fail. Optimising energy is one of the greatest challenges for reducing climate impacts and SCORES is demonstrating what can be possible in terms of the changes we all desire.

SCORES consortium meeting and workshops in the new hybrid way of working setting, October 2021, Amsterdam & online.